

INPLASY

Leadership, human-centered management and organizational culture: Pathways to well-being and innovative work based on a systematic review

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ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

Support - None.

Review Stage at time of this submission - Completed but not published.

Conflicts of interest - None declared.

INPLASY registration number: INPLASY2025100101

Amendments - This protocol was registered with the International Platform of Registered Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (INPLASY) on 25 October 2025 and was last updated on 25 October 2025.

INTRODUCTION

Review question / Objective Research Question How do leadership and organizational culture shape workplace well-being and innovative behavior in contexts of technological transformation?

Objective This study examines the literature on workplace well-being, leadership, organizational culture, and human-centered management in the context of technological transformation. It explores how innovation and digitalization influence human sustainability and proposes an integrated conceptual model linking leadership, psychosocial mechanisms, well-being, and innovative behavior.

Rationale Digital transformation is reshaping work and management, yet evidence on its human consequences is fragmented across studies of well-being, leadership, culture, and human-

centered management. Prior reviews often isolate single pathways that link managerial practices to well-being and innovative behavior.

Condition being studied Not applicable.

METHODS

Search strategy SCOPUS: Your query: (TITLE-ABS-KEY (well-being; AND innovation; AND organization) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "BUSI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "re")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))).

Participant or population Organizations, managers, employees.

Intervention Not applicable.

Comparator Not applicable.

Study designs to be included Studies published in the SCOPUS database between 1989 and February 2025.

Eligibility criteria Inclusion Criteria:

- Primary studies relevant to the research topic;
- Studies with direct and/or indirect identification of the public and/or private sectors;
- Articles written in English.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Letters, conference abstracts, theses, media reports, and content feeds;
- Articles not centered on the studied theme.

Information sources Electronic databases (SCOPUS).

Main outcome(s) None.

Data management 1-Removal of Duplicated Literature

2- Screening Steps:

The selection process will follow three sequential steps:

- (1) Title Screening:

Article titles will be assessed based on exclusion criteria, ensuring irrelevant studies are discarded at this initial stage.

- (2) Abstract Screening:

Abstracts of selected articles will be analyzed to verify their relevance against the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

- (3) Full-Text Screening:

Full texts of articles that pass the abstract screening will be evaluated against the established eligibility criteria. Only studies meeting all criteria will be included in the review.

3- Reviewer Agreement:

The screening process will be conducted by two independent reviewers. Screening will commence only after achieving at least 75% agreement between reviewers in a pilot test applied to a sample of articles to ensure consistency in applying the criteria. In case of discrepancies, a third reviewer will be consulted to resolve conflicts.

4- Reporting Research Results:

The results of the selection process will be presented in the PRISMA-ScR (PRISMA Extended Scoping Review) flow diagram. This flowchart will detail the screening stages, from the initial number of identified studies to the final articles included in the review, with justification provided for exclusions at each stage.

5-Data Recording and Exportation:

All information regarding selected articles, rejected articles, and reasons for exclusion will be recorded in an Excel file. This record will be used for future analysis and as documentation for auditing the review process.

All relevant abstracts and manuscripts will be saved in a password protected computer. A data extraction Excel template will be created to collect pertinent information as the investigators review manuscripts.

Quality assessment / Risk of bias analysis Two reviewers will independently assess the risk of bias using for the analysis of: qualitative articles the guidelines defined by Letts et al. (2007); for quantitative articles the paper by Law et al. (1998) will be used and AMSTAR-2 (Shea et al., 2017) grid for systematic review articles.

Strategy of data synthesis

1- Thematic Analysis and Data Coding

2- Synthesis of Findings by Category

- Effective Strategies and Interventions: Synthesize organizational interventions

3- Validation and Final Reporting

- A critical analysis of the identified gaps in the literature will be conducted, highlighting areas for future research and emphasizing the practical implications of the findings for organizations.

Subgroup analysis The findings of the systematic review will be organized and presented through tables and figures, complemented by a descriptive analysis to synthesize and interpret the data effectively.

Sensitivity analysis The PRISMA-ScR (2020) framework will be utilized to guide and document the selection and reporting process for the systematic review. This approach ensures transparency, replicability, and a comprehensive account of how evidence was identified, screened, and included.

Language restriction English language sources only.

Country(ies) involved Portugal - University of Lisbon, Institute of Social and Political Sciences.

Keywords Workplace well-being; innovative work behavior; human-centered management; organizational culture; leadership; work motivation; digital transformation; artificial intelligence; responsible innovation.

Dissemination plans We plan to disseminate the findings through abstract submission and manuscript publication in appropriate venues and journals.

Contributions of each author

Author 1 - Paulo Diniz - Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Software; Writing - revision and editing.

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Author 2 - Isabel Marques - Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Acquisition of funding; Methodology; Supervision; Writing - revision and editing.

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